

Kinetic Salt Effect. Part III. Influence of Non-electrolytes on Salt Effect in Ionic Reactions.

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It was shown in a previous communication from this laboratory that the variation of the kinetic activity factor with total ionic strength in the reaction between monobromacetate and thiosulphate ions is in good agreement with the variation rate calculated on the basis of Debye-Hückel limitation equation for the activity coefficient of an ion in dilute solutions up to a total ionic strength of 0.014μ (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 45). This simple method of testing theory by velocity measurements can advantageously be extended to non-aqueous solutions or solutions in mixed solvents.

In the equation deduced from Brönsted's (or Soper's) theory, for aqueous solutions in the neighbourhood of 25° ,

$$\log K = \text{Constant} \pm Z_A Z_B \sqrt{\mu} \quad \dots (1)$$

we see that the velocity constant would be affected if to the reaction mixture we were to add an electrolyte, be it one of the reacting components or a neutral salt. On the other hand, the addition of a non-electrolyte should have no effect. It should be remembered at the same time that the above equation has been deduced on the basis of Debye's equation for the activity coefficient of an ion,

$$-\log f_i = \frac{\epsilon^2 - z^2}{2DkT} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\epsilon^2}{DkT} \sum n_i z_i^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

which shows that the dielectric constant of the ionising medium has a profound influence on the activity coefficient of an ion and consequently on the variation of the kinetic activity factor. It is well-known that non-electrolytes like alcohol and cane sugar lower the dielectric constant of water to a considerable extent. From the standpoint of equation (1) all that can be said therefore is that so

long as the amount of non-electrolyte added to an aqueous solution is not too great to bring about a change in the nature of the solvent, its influence on the activity coefficient of any one of the ions or the kinetic activity factor may be negligible. But, when the amount of non-electrolyte added is large enough, the lowering in the dielectric constant becomes marked and from theory we should expect a marked difference in the variation of the kinetic activity factor, whatever the effect of the non-electrolyte on the velocity constant at a particular total ionic concentration may be.

While the need for more data in pure aqueous solutions concerning ions of different characteristics remains, it can be said that so far as aqueous solutions are concerned, the investigations of Brönsted and La Mer and others (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 555) have provided ample material in proof of Debye-Hückel theory. The same, however, cannot be said of solvents other than water or solvent mixtures having water as one of the components. Attempts have been made by Scatchard (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **47**, 2098 ; Noyes and Baxter (*ibid*, 1925, **47**, 2122) and Nonhebel and Hartley (*Phil. Mag.*, 1925, **50**, 2122) among others to test the validity of Debye's theory in mixtures of alcohol and water and pure alcohols. They considered the data for hydrochloric acid in these different solvents and found that even in the case of this simple uni-univalent electrolyte, the agreement between theory and experimental results was not close. More recently Brönsted and Williams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 1338) have found from solubility measurements that in aqueous-alcoholic and sugar solutions, the agreement between theory and experiment, though not quantitative, is yet not satisfactory. In view of the paucity of data on the effect of non-electrolytes on the activity coefficients of ions of different valence types in aqueous solutions, velocity measurements of ionic reactions in solvent mixtures would afford valuable evidence either for or against equation (2).

The present investigation was undertaken with the object of studying the kinetics of the reaction between monobromacetate and thiosulphate ions, from the above standpoint, in mixtures of alcohol and water and cane sugar and water, as the dielectric constants of these mixtures are fairly well known. This reaction, a detailed investigation of which was reported in Part II (*loc. cit.*) is quite suitable for our purpose as both the reacting components are quite neutral towards the non-electrolytes, alcohol and sugar.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The way in which the reaction was followed was the same as in Part II, the usual precautions for the purification of the materials necessary being observed.

Aqueous—Alcoholic Solutions.—Measurements have been made with pure water. 20% 40%, 60% and 80% alcoholic solutions (the figures refer to volume per cent.). Tables I-IX give data obtained with 80% alcoholic solutions at 25°. The symbols T and Br are employed in the following tables for thiosulphate and bromacetate respectively.

TABLE I.

Ionic strength = 0.05 μ ; 10 c.c. titrated.

Time in minutes.	T.	Br.	K.
0	8.45 c.c.	18.45 c.c.	—
10	7.25	17.25	0.8579
20	6.30	16.30	0.8487
30	5.50	15.50	0.8510
40	4.80	14.80	0.8625
50	4.25	14.25	0.8556
70	3.35	13.35	0.8579
			Mean 0.8556

TABLE II.

Ionic strength = 0.035 μ ; 10 c.c. titrated.

Time in minutes.	T.	Br.	K.
0	9.55 c.c.	4.55 c.c.	—
30	8.75	3.75	0.7052
60	8.15	3.15	0.6969
90	7.65	2.65	0.7079
150	6.95	1.95	0.7098
210	6.50	1.50	0.6900
360	5.80	0.80	0.6900
			Mean 0.6989

TABLE III.
 $\text{CH}_2\text{Br.COONa} = 0.008M$; $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.004M$.
 Ionic strength = 0.02μ ; 25 c.c. titrated.

Time in minutes.	T.	Br.	K
0	9.80 c.c.	19.80 c.c.	—
30	8.55	18.55	0.5922
60	7.50	17.50	0.5983
90	6.35	16.65	0.5945
120	5.95	15.95	0.5750
200	4.50	14.50	0.5825
380	2.50	12.50	0.5951
			Mean 0.5981

TABLE IV.
 $\text{CH}_2\text{Br.COONa} = 0.002M$; $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.004M$;
 Ionic strength = 0.014μ ; 25 c.c. titrated.

Time in min.	T.	Br.	K.
0	9.90 c.c.	4.90 c.c.	—
60	9.40	4.40	0.4638
150	8.75	3.75	0.4798
250	8.20	3.20	0.4726
420	7.50	2.50	0.4680
600	6.95	1.95	0.4726
			Mean 0.4713

TABLE V.
 $\text{CH}_2\text{Br.COONa} = 0.004M$; $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.002M$;
 Ionic strength = 0.01μ ; 50 c.c. titrated.

Time in min.	T.	Br.	K.
0	9.90 c.c.	19.90 c.c.	—
60	8.95	18.95	0.4312
120	8.15	18.15	0.4266
180	7.40	17.40	0.4347
300	6.25	16.25	0.4289
520	4.65	14.65	0.4312
750	3.50	13.50	0.4355
			Mean 0.4310

TABLE VI.

 $\text{CH}_2\text{Br.COONa} = 0.001M$; $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.0025M$.Ionic strength = 0.0085μ ; 100 c.c. titrated.

Time in min.	T.	Br.	K.
0	24.90 c.c.	9.90 c.c.	—
100	24.00	9.00	0.3910
200	23.15	8.15	0.4039
300	22.45	7.45	0.4010
450	21.55	6.55	0.3986
600	20.75	5.75	0.4002
750	20.10	5.10	0.3986
		Mean	0.3990

TABLE VII.

 $\text{CH}_2\text{Br.COONa} = 0.001M$; $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.002M$;Ionic strength = 0.007μ ; 50 c.c. titrated.

0	9.90 c.c.	4.90 c.c.	—
120	9.50	4.50	0.3660
180	9.325	4.325	0.3657
300	9.00	4.000	0.3591
420	8.70	3.70	0.3634
600	8.30	3.30	0.3648
1440	7.10	2.10	0.3585
		Mean	0.3626

TABLE VIII.

 $\text{CH}_2\text{Br.COONa} = 0.002M$; $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.001M$;Ionic strength = 0.305μ ; 50 c.c. titrated.

0	4.95 c.c.	9.95 c.c.	0.3045
240	4.30	9.30	0.3089
480	3.80	8.80	0.3089
750	3.30	8.30	0.2990
1550	2.30	7.30	0.3044
2160	1.75	6.75	0.3013
		Mean	0.3036

TABLE IX.

$\text{CH}_2\text{Br.COO}\text{Na} = 0.001M$; $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.0005M$;
 Ionic strength = 0.0025μ ; 100 c.c. titrated.

Time in min.	T.	Br.	K.
0	4.875 c.c.	9.875 c.c.	—
250	4.60	9.60	0.2337
480	4.375	9.375	0.2309
780	4.10	9.10	0.2323
1500	3.55	8.55	0.2300
2160	3.10	8.10	0.2346
			Mean 0.2323

Table X contains a summary of data obtained with the different alcoholic solutions. The data with pure aqueous solutions are also included for purposes of comparison.

TABLE X.

Velocity Constants.

μ	Water.	20% .	40% .	60% .	80% .
0.0025	0.2970	0.2576	0.2093	0.2136	0.2323
0.005	0.3306	0.3059	0.2599	0.2716	0.3036
0.007	0.3511	0.3427	0.3082	0.3176	0.3626
0.0085	0.3615	0.3680	0.3289	0.3528	0.3990
0.010	0.3727	0.3841	0.3473	0.3841	0.4310
0.014	0.3029	0.4117	0.3841	0.4299	0.4713
0.020	0.4288	0.4531	0.4554	0.4745	0.5891
0.035	0.4825	0.5124	0.5313	0.5704	0.6989
0.050	0.5244	0.5474	0.5796	0.6532	0.8556
0.070	0.5571	0.5635	0.6357	0.7406	—
0.085	0.5923	0.5885	0.6601	—	—

A glance at the table shows that no general relationship can be drawn between the concentration of alcohol and its effect upon the velocity constant. In a 20% solution of alcohol the velocity at lower concentrations is decidedly lesser than in aqueous solutions up to about 0.010μ and beyond this concentration the velocity is slightly higher than in aqueous solutions. In a 40% solution of alcohol up to 0.014μ the velocity constants have values

lower still than in 20% alcoholic solutions and then the values rise much higher. In 60% alcoholic solutions, below 0.01μ the velocity constants are lower than in aqueous solutions and then they rise higher whereas throughout the range examined the values are always higher than in 40% solution. In 80% solution the constants are always very much higher than in 60% solution. The velocity constants except for 0.0025μ and 0.005μ , are even very much higher throughout than in water. It thus becomes clear that it is unsafe to conclude from a series of measurements at any particular ionic strength with solvent mixtures of different compositions, anything with regard to the relationship between the concentration of the non-electrolyte and the velocity of the reaction. Senter (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1071) found in his study of the reaction between sodium monobromacetate and sodium methoxide in aqueous-alcoholic solutions that the reaction proceeded with the maximum velocity in a 60% alcoholic solution (Senter's results were confined only to one total ionic concentration.) The first, second, third and fourth horizontal columns in Table X show that the velocity constant passes through a minimum in a 40% alcoholic solution. The same can be said to be the case with the 5th and 6th columns, if we exclude the data for water. The remaining columns do not show any maximum or minimum points. In these cases the velocity progressively increases with the increase in alcohol content of the solvent.

Debye-Hückel slopes.—We have seen before that in the case of pure aqueous solutions, $\frac{d \log k}{d \sqrt{\mu}}$ found is almost exactly equal to the calculated Debye-Hückel slope. Fig. 1 gives the curves in which $\log K$ is plotted against $\sqrt{\mu}$ for dilute solutions in aqueous alcohol—water mixtures. Table XI gives the calculated and experimentally determined slopes.

TABLE XI.

Alcohol.	Slope (found).	Slope (calc.).	Difference.
20%	3.75	2.50	50%
40%	4.66	3.21	48.2%
60%	5.10	4.45	14.60%
80%	5.75	6.65	13.50%

For the calculations involved, the values for the dielectric constants of the alcoholic mixtures have been taken from the paper of

Fürth (*Ann. Physik*, 1923, 70, 33). The values of Fürth coincide almost with the results of Nernst (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1890, 14, 660). It will be seen that in 20, 40 and 60 per cent. alcoholic mixtures of water the slopes found are very much higher than the calculated slopes, while in 80% solution the reverse is the case. In 20 and 40 per cent. solutions the divergence from theory is very great while in 60 and 80 per cent. solutions it is not very great. However, even in the last two cases, the agreement with theory cannot be said to be even a rough one. Brönsted and Williams (*loc. cit.*) found from solubility measurements that the Debye-Hückel slopes calculated from theory differed from experimental ones by about 10-15%. Yet assuming that there was some uncertainty about the values of the dielectric constants of the mixtures, they concluded that their results are in agreement with the Debye-Hückel theory. It appears to the author, however, that it is a little too much to assume that the dielectric constant measurements are so much in error. So far as the velocity measurements of the present investigation indicate, Debye-Hückel theory does not quantitatively predict the course of the reaction, although the slopes are in the direction indicated by the theory. Table XII gives the velocity constants at different ionic concentrations in the different alcoholic solvents at 35°.

FIG. 1.

TABLE XII.

Velocity Constants.

μ .	20%.	40%.	60%.	80%.
0.0025	0.5428	0.4255	0.5018	0.5405
0.0050	0.6440	0.5267	0.6410	0.7047
0.007	0.7199	0.6187	0.7463	0.8418
0.0085	0.7820	0.6624	0.8255	0.9287
0.010	0.8078	0.7015	0.9050	1.0005
0.014	0.8625	0.7682	1.0106	1.2010
0.020	0.9522	0.9200	1.1178	1.3800
0.035	0.0787	1.0695	1.3404	1.6054
0.050	1.1500	1.1730	1.5295	1.9842
0.070	1.1833	1.2765	1.7273	—
0.085	1.2254	1.3363	—	—

Table XIII gives the temperature coefficients $K_{35^\circ}/K_{25^\circ}$ in these different cases.

TABLE XIII.

 $K_{35^\circ}/K_{25^\circ}$.

μ .	20%.	40%.	60%.	80%.
0.0025	2.107	2.033	2.347	2.320
0.0050	2.105	2.024	2.360	2.321
0.0070	2.100	2.007	2.349	2.321
0.0085	2.127	2.014	2.311	2.327
0.0100	2.091	2.019	2.356	2.321
0.0140	2.095	2.000	2.350	2.550
0.0200	2.102	2.020	2.355	2.342
0.0350	2.105	2.013	2.349	2.297
0.0500	2.108	2.024	2.340	2.319
0.0700	2.100	2.008	2.322	—
0.0850	2.098	2.024	—	—
Mean	2.108	2.017	2.344	2.321

It is to be observed that as in the case of aqueous solutions, in these cases also the temperature coefficient over the entire range of ionic concentrations remains absolutely steady. But each alcoholic solution has its own temperature coefficient. This is of course to be expected but it is rather queer that there is no regularity about the variation of the temperature coefficient with the percentage of alcohol.

Cane Sugar Solutions.

Fürth has also determined the dielectric constants of solutions of cane sugar in water. It is possible to prepare cane sugar solutions having the same dielectric constants as certain alcoholic solutions and it was thought that velocity measurements in these sugar mixtures might throw some light on the point whether the velocity at any ionic concentration is determined by factors other than dielectric constant. From this standpoint cane sugar solutions serve a very useful purpose as they happen to be very viscous as compared with water-alcohol mixtures. Table XIV gives the data at 25° with 30% and 50% (by weight) sugar solutions.

TABLE XIV.

Velocity Constants.

μ .	30% sugar.	50% sugar.
0.0025	0.2820	0.2690
0.005	0.3320	0.3372
0.007	0.3491	0.3681
0.010	0.3832	0.4159
0.014	0.4180	0.4395
0.020	0.4613	0.4820
0.035	0.5290	0.5701

Here also, as in the case of alcoholic solutions, we find that initially, *i.e.*, at low concentrations, the velocity constants are lower than in the case of pure water but soon they begin to rise and go above the values in water as the ionic concentration rises. The

rate of rise in 50% sugar solutions is very much higher than in 30% solutions. The 30% and 50% sugar solutions have dielectric constants 67 and 49 respectively. For these mixtures the calculated Debye-Hückel slopes in the ideal region are 2.568 and 4.104 respectively. Curves obtained by plotting the data in Table XIV give

for $\frac{d \log k}{d \sqrt{\mu}}$ the values 2.6 and 3.6 for 30% and 50% sugar solutions

respectively. In the first case the agreement with theory is excellent while in the latter case the divergence is not much as compared with the divergences observed in the case of alcoholic solutions. It can therefore be said that so far as the ions in our reaction are concerned, up to a limit of about 0.015μ and 0.010μ in the cases of 30% and 50% sugar solutions respectively (deduced from graphs), the Debye-Hückel expression fairly quantitatively predicts the courses of the reaction.

It is to be observed at the same time that viscosity does not seem to have any marked effect on the velocity of reaction.

Summary.

(1) A study of the kinetics of the reaction between monobromacetate and thiosulphate ions has been made at various ionic concentrations beginning from 0.0025μ in 20%, 40%, 60% and 80% solutions of alcohol in water and in 30% and 50% solutions of sugar in water.

(2) The temperature coefficients of the rates of reaction at the different ionic concentrations and in the different alcoholic solvents have been measured. The temperature coefficient remains absolutely steady in the same solvent over the entire range of ionic concentrations. The reaction velocity has a definite temperature coefficient in each of the solvents, but there is no regularity in the variation of the temperature coefficient with the percentage of alcohol.

(3) The slopes $\left(\frac{d \log k}{d \sqrt{\mu}} \right)$ found in the case 20 and 40 per cent.

mixtures of alcohol in water are nearly 50% greater than the slopes calculated on the basis of Debye-Hückel limitation equation, while the slope in 60% alcohol is 15% higher and in 80% alcohol it is 14% lesser than the calculated slopes.

(4) No general relationship could be traced between the percentage of alcohol and the velocity constant although some regularity may be found at any particular ionic concentration.

(5) The results obtained with sugar solutions show greater agreement with Debye-Hückel theory. The values of $\left(\frac{d \log k}{d \sqrt{\mu}}\right)$ found in the case of 30% and 50% sugar solutions are 2.6 and 3.6 respectively while the calculated values are 2.568 and 4.104 respectively. The viscosity of sugar solutions does not seem to affect the velocity of reaction to any appreciable extent.

I have enjoyed the privilege of discussing the several problems connected with the velocity of ionic reactions with my professor, Dr. J. C. Ghosh. I take this opportunity of expressing my gratitude to him for the kind interest he has taken in my work.

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